

ISic3010

I.Sicily inscription 3010

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone (Taormina)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ortygia, from demolition of 16th cent. fortifications at entrance to
island

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6288

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140295

1. [Ἀγαθῶ]ι Δαίμονι
2. [— — —]εος οἱ υἱοὶ
3. [— — —]Ι Σῆμος,
4. [Ἀρί]στων
- 5.

Edition: PHI331256

1. [Ἀγαθῶ]ι Δαίμονι
2. [— — κλ]εος οἱ υἱοὶ
3. [— — —] Η, Σῆμος
4. [— — — —] υτων.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645358

PHI 140295

PHI 331256

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0005a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 34.0988

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 466

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 370

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